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The political control: problem statement

Abstract. Political control as a special phenomenon is deeply hidden in complex social life. However, its influence is noticeable in many countries of the world. In this regard, there is a need for a more detailed study of this phenomenon from the point of view of setting limits to the permissible impact of the state through political control on society. At present, the influence of the masses on socio-political processes is significantly increasing. Consequently, this is the reason for the growing interest in ways of political control. As social life becomes more complex, a new direction in science is emerging that synthesizes the results of historical, legal, political science, and sociological research. This new direction becomes the subject of this research.

Key words: political control, supervision on population, political loyalty, political investigation, repression.

Political control is a phenomenon that lies on the surface and is deeply veiled in multi-layered social life. It is impossible to ignore its coverage in history, since historical experience must be taken into account when building a rule-of-law state and civil society.

We believe that the main purpose of political control is to provide the current government with objective information about the political moods of the subordinate population in order to make the necessary adjustments to the current political course.

The dramatic increase in the control functions of the modern state gives relevance to the scientific analysis of the problem under consideration and determines the selection of new aspects in its study. It is important to study the historical experience of political control from the point of view of determining the limits of permissible state influence by means of political control on society.

Another characteristic that determined the relevance of the study of this problem is the international feature. Throughout the world, in the twentieth century, the influence of the masses on the sociopolitical processes increased significantly. In this regard, inter-

est in methods of political control has increased significantly, the use of which in a short period allows us to bring the value system of the overwhelming majority of people closer to the norms desired or directly determined by the authorities. In connection with the rapid development of mass communication and the creation of the information society, favorable conditions were created for the implementation of political control by manipulating ideas and images, both rooted in the distant past and newly created by the authorities. These methods are used both domestically and internationally.

Politics, the state, the authorities traditionally play a leading role in the development of Russian society due to its historical, cultural, territorial, geographical features. The existence of a traditionally strong power in Russia contributes to the mobilization of the population and its organizations to carry out large-scale economic work, to protect the borders, to colonize new lands. This requires the maintenance of high authority of the state power and its carriers in the public realization.

The attitude to the control system and the mechanism of its functioning was differ-

ent at one or another stage of statehood development, changes in economic, and, therefore, political life, however, the desire of the ruling regimes to receive timely information about the state of affairs in the country remained unchanged.

Attempts to introduce political control were made by Peter I, who forced the priests to violate the secrets of confession and forced their members to attend church services without fail. In the 20th century, we have a much more complicated phenomenon - the introduction of ideology is added to the actual control, i.e. mass indoctrination of the population, formation, modeling of mass consciousness, stereotypes of the desired behavior. If in the first half of the XX century this phenomenon was mainly inherent in the totalitarian regimes, then in the second half of the century practically all developed states began to engage in the modeling of mass consciousness.

In the modern state, the function of political control (supervision) is preserved, only its content, forms, methods and intensity change.

It is the key role of political control (supervision) in ensuring public and state security that determines the relevance of the research topic.

The practice of controlling the mood of the population and the desire to constructively influence them is perceived as specific to Russia. However, in reality, it is of a wider, general European or even global character. Thus, in the period between the two world wars, totalitarian measures in essence were carried out by both Nazi Germany and the stronghold of liberalism - England.

Supervision over the mood of the population, therefore, should be understood not only as a «Russian phenomenon», but as an auxiliary function of the Politics of the modern era, one of the variants of which is totalitarianism.

Such a Policy is a tool for the formation of society, as well as a tool to influence the population in order to make its ideal a reality.

Control (supervision) of the population in any of the states is not passive observation. It serves the purposes of effective man-

agement, and therefore is constructive. Political power imposes a certain «discourse» in society, certain forms of self-expression and self-identification, and, thus, power control is introduced into the consciousness of every person.

Political control (supervision) involves the cooperation of several state structures, including, of course, political special services, and is an integral part of social control, like organizing a person's mastering of a certain culture, introducing a certain lifestyle, applying sanctions to individuals or groups of individuals them of one or another social norm.

The supervision of the population is not only intended to identify the opinions and attitudes of the population, as it is not reduced to simply controlling this population. Its main purpose is to influence people in order to change their consciousness and behavior. That is, surveillance activities include attempts to gather information about the mood of the population, and measures aimed at transforming these sentiments.

The concept of population surveillance means a special type of collection and processing of information about the entire population of public sentiment for various political purposes. That is, population surveillance is a collection of information, not for the sake of simply describing the state of people's minds, but in order to manage this state and give it a certain form. The state begins to strive to control the population subject to it, not so much in accordance with the principles of law and justice, as in accordance with the principles of efficiency and economy.

Supervision (control) of the mood of the population is not intended primarily to study public opinion, nor is it a preventive, protective measure aimed at preventing any opposition speeches (although, of course, it was used in these purposes too). Supervision was a set of practical measures needed to accomplish the task of redesigning society and transforming each of its individual members.

Thus, political control is understood by us not only as direct control over the behavior and political loyalty of individuals, but

also as a way for the authorities to influence the mass consciousness of people. Political control is an inherent characteristic of absolutely any state. Only scales, forms and methods of its realization are crucial.

At the same time, any system of political control (supervision) exploits a person's natural psychological needs: for security; in belonging to a community; in respect, in recognition; in self-realization; in positive emotions. Using political control and without resorting to significant material costs, the authorities can solve a few problems facing it: to mobilize the population of the country to achieve certain goals; to distance themselves from almost any negative phenomena, and, thus, to smooth out the intra-state conflict between the government and society, etc. At the same time, the authorities, eliminating a possible conflict, at the same time receive a kind of authority to apply emergency measures, including terror, arguing that they must be applied by the presence of a threat (real or imaginary) to society.

Political control is one of the inalienable functions of the state, it originates with the emergence of the state and develops as social life becomes more complex. For many centuries, political control was carried out primarily in the form of political investigation, using repression against extremist anti-government groups.

Gradually, its functions are becoming increasingly diverse. In the twentieth century, real participation in the daily political life of millions of people in an increasing number of countries, the growing dependence of political regimes on the sentiments of the broadest masses, manifested either through an election mechanism or methods of extra-parliamentary opposition, presented new demands for political control.

Now individuals and social groups under social control, while they themselves are involved in its implementation and form the ways in which it is carried out. That is, being under social control, his «passive victims» at the same time participate in the process of its implementation and create forms of control, under which they themselves.

That is, there is a link between population surveillance and social control over society.

Therefore political control should provide the country's leadership not only with information about terrorist and opposition groups, etc., but also provide the government with objective information about political sympathies and antipathies of the population, its reaction to certain actions of the authorities, constantly monitor changes in attitudes regions and social strata, thus creating the opportunity for the necessary adjustment of the political course produced by the authorities.

Since for absolutely any state, the task of protecting the foundations of a sociopolitical system from the encroachments of extremist anti-government groups is topical, society is forced to sanction the use of hidden, secret forms of political control by the state to ensure the harmony and stability of its development. However, their implementation involves the possibility of invasion into the sphere of the declared and guaranteed by the state personal rights and freedoms of a person and citizen (secret correspondence, telephone conversations, inviolability of the home, etc.). Therefore, such an invasion should be legally restricted.

The author believes that political control is a system of regular collection and analysis of information by various branches of the state apparatus about attitudes in society, its various attitudes to the actions of the authorities, about the behavior and intentions of extremist and antigovernment groups and organizations, which includes the following main elements: information gathering, assessment, decision-making, taking into account relevant sentiments, political investigation and repression.

Specifically, political control is a complex of government measures aimed not only at controlling the behavior of an individual, of all social groups, but also at shaping the worldview and behavior of most of the population based on the given ideological canons and practical needs of the regime to create a mass pillar of power.

Political control means analytic-preventive activities of the state, carried out by special units of the state apparatus, with the assistance of other bodies of state power and administration, with the participation of public structures and individual citizens, in order to fulfill the function of preserving the foundations of the existing socio-political system.

Political control is a system of regular collection, evaluation and analysis of information coordinated by political intelligence bodies (political police) by various branches of the state apparatus and specialized public structures about attitudes in society, making decisions that take into account the attitudes of public groups and are designed to influence attitudes of various sectors of society to the actions of the authorities and the intentions of extremist and antigovernment groups and organizations. Political control smoothly flows directly into the political search (spying) with the further use of repression when a threat is detected (real or imaginary) to the state and society.

When social control of the population depends on the media, and not only on intelligence data, the tasks of the political investigation are shifted towards monitoring public opinion and attitudes in society, and especially towards radical groups, who are often deprived of such a tribune as the media, therefore they have to declare about yourself aggressive memorable actions and even terrorist acts.

Unquestionably, without abolishing repression, modern political control implies a definite bias towards analyzing the public reaction to decisions taken by the country's leadership from the standpoint of ensuring the country's security, as well as the participation of political intelligence bodies in developing the main directions of national policy in terms of its impact on social stability and sustainability of the state and society.

Political control is an integral element of state power, one of the important elements of its functioning due to the desire of the government to obtain objective and reliable information about various aspects of society.

In a conclusion, we can note the following:

First, control in its broad sense is an integral attribute of the state under any type of political regime. Moreover, it is one of the most important elements of its functioning due to the desire of the ruling elite to obtain accurate, objective and reliable information about various aspects of the life of society and the activities of the state bureaucracy.

This striving, in turn, is determined by the striving to preserve and hold political power from any kind of encroachment, including from opposition groups and dissenters. In this regard, the state creates an appropriate apparatus of political control, which should have sufficient forces and means to ensure state and public security, to minimize all possible types of probable threats.

Secondly, the forms, methods and scope, the scale of political control, as the goals and objectives of political investigation, are determined by the ruling elite, depending on the type of political regime. Totalitarian, authoritarian and democratic regimes are building the corresponding control system. At the same time, one of the fundamental criteria of distinction is the attitude to legality in the functioning of the system of control and political intelligence.

The violation of rights and freedoms by established regimes of power, for all its unethically, is a consequence of the state's attitudes, and it almost always sanctions and carries out the actions that are necessary, from his point of view, to ensure their own security.

Thirdly, the bodies of political investigation are the direct main instrument for exercising political control. The quality of their activities is determined and depends on the state, the ruling elite, defining the goals, objectives and principles of its activities.

The theoretical foundations of the implementation of control are closely related to the trends in the economic, social, and cultural development of the state, which must adequately evaluate them. Otherwise, there may be a drop in the effectiveness of political control and activity of political intelligence in its implementation due to the di-

vergence of its theoretical and methodological basis with the realities of the country's development.

The development of political control shows that at certain stages their quality of functioning may fall. But almost always, due to the understanding by the state authorities of the tasks facing it, these institutions find new forms and methods of control, corresponding to reality.

In general, the theoretical basis of political control may have multivariate schemes with the dominance of the goal of protecting the state system. Activities for its implementation largely depends on obtaining reliable information about the mood of the population, the activities of opposition groups, trends in dissent.

Allocate the so-called police oversight of the population, that is, the collection of individual information about the opponents of the existing system as a preventive measure with the possibility of using against dissident repression, as well as government supervision - the collection of information to familiarize with the mood of the population and manage them.

Methods and forms of obtaining information and ensuring state security are correlated by the state, the ruling elite, depending on the ideas about the objectives of this activity. The main trend in the development of political control and bodies of political investigation can be called all the increased specialization of their activities using advanced methods and technologies.

In this regard, the effectiveness of the political control bodies, the functioning of the entire system is closely related to the quality of the ruling elite, its desire and ability to react in a timely and effective manner to certain situations, thereby setting the parameters for the political control system.

This aspect is manifested in the practical actions of the state security agencies, their daily work to curb the activities of anti-government groups, opposition movements, or other forms of dissent.

In general, the system of political control and bodies of political investigation, being derived from the political regime, the internal political course pursued by the government, are a necessary element of the state mechanism.

REFERENCES

1. Allen W. Hannah Arendt and the ideological structure of totalitarianism // *Man and World*. April 1993. Volume 26. Issue 2. Pp. 115-129.
2. Holquist P. Information Is the Alpha and Omega of Our Work»: Bolshevik Surveillance in Its Pan-European Context // *The Journal of Modern History*. Volume 69. Number 3. (Sep., 1997). Pp. 415-427.
3. Kaes A. The Cold Gaze. Notes on Mobilization and Modernity // *New German Critique*. Volume 59 (Special Issue on Ernst Junger), 1993. P. 116.
4. Social Control in Europe. 1500-1800 / Roodenburg H., Spierenburg P. and Spierenburg C. ed. Volume 1. Columbus: Ohio State University Press, 2004. 381 p.
5. Social Control in Europe. 1800-2000 / Emsley C., Johnson E. and Spierenburg P. ed. Volume 2. Columbus: Ohio State University Press, 2005. 445 P.
6. The French Revolution and the Creation of Modern Political Culture: The Political Culture of the Old Regime / Bekker K.M. ed. Vol. I. Oxford-New York: Pergamon Press, 1987. 559 p.

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